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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF DICLOFENAC
SODIUM PRONIOSOMES****Mrs.T.Sowmya*, Dr.T.Mangilal, Sadiya Begum, Gonela Sharvani, K.Uma Maheshwari,
Kanduri Pravallika, K.Hemalatha**Smt.sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy, Seshadrinagar, Mahabubnagar-509001,
Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

Approaches are being adapted to achieve this goal, by paying considerable attention either to control the distribution of drug by incorporating it in a carrier system, or by altering the structure of the drug at the molecular level, or to control the input of the drug into the bioenvironment to ensure an appropriate profile of distribution. Different types of pharmaceutical carriers are present. They are – particulate, polymeric, macromolecular, and cellular carrier. Particulate type carriers also known as a colloidal carrier system, include lipid particles (low- and high-density lipoprotein-LDL and HDL, respectively), microspheres, nanoparticles, polymeric micelles and vesicular like liposomes, niosomes, pharmacosomes, virosomes, etc. Diclofenac sodium loaded proniosomes can be prepared by slurry method with Span 80 and cholesterol in the ratio of 1:1, 2:1, and 1:2. The powder is smooth surface both visually and microscopically. The main objective of the present study was to perform the drug entrapment study by aqueous drug determination method. There are two methods available to carry out drug entrapment studies. They are aqueous drug determination method and lysis method. The former method is involved in the estimation of untrapped drug while the latter method is based on the drug entrapped in the vesicles. The latter method need the sample to be dialysed to remove untrapped drug. Moreover, there may be some chance of hindrances in the spectroscopic determination of drug along with the lysing agent in the sample. Niosomal dispersions were obtained when different volumes (5,10 and 10 ml) were added to proniosome powder. High % drug entrapment was observed in the formulation PRNIO 3. Osmotic shock studies on vesicles showed that no significant change in the niosomal preparation was stored at normal saline.

Key Words: LDL, HDL, Span 80, Proniosomes, Diclofenac sodium**Corresponding author:****T.Sowmya,**Smt.sarojini ramulamma college of pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

In the past few decades, considerable attention has been focused on the development of a new drug delivery system (NDDS). The NDDS should ideally fulfill two prerequisites. Firstly, it should deliver the drug at a rate directed by the needs of the body, over the period of treatment. Secondly, it should channel the active entity to the site of action. Conventional dosage forms including prolonged release dosage forms are unable to meet none of these. At present, no available drug delivery system behaves ideally, but sincere attempts have been made to achieve them through various novel approaches in drug delivery.

Approaches are being adapted to achieve this goal, by paying considerable attention either to control the distribution of drug by incorporating it in a carrier system, or by altering the structure of the drug at the molecular level, or to control the input of the drug into the bioenvironmental to ensure an appropriate profile of distribution.

Different types of pharmaceutical carriers are present. They are – particulate, polymeric, macromolecular, and cellular carrier. Particulate type carriers also known as a colloidal carrier system, include lipid particles (low- and high-density lipoprotein-LDL and HDL, respectively), microspheres, nanoparticles, polymeric micelles and vesicular like liposomes, niosomes, pharmacosomes, virosomes, etc. The vesicular systems are highly ordered assemblies of one or several concentric lipid bilayers formed, when certain amphiphilic building blocks are confronted with water. Vesicles can be formed from a diverse range of amphiphilic building blocks. The terms such as synthetic bilayers allude to the non-biological origin of such vesiculogenesis.²

Vesicular Systems¹

In recent years, vesicles have become the vehicle of choice in drug delivery. Lipid vesicles were found to be value in immunology, membrane biology, diagnostic techniques, and most recently, genetic engineering. Vesicles can play a major role in modeling biological membranes, and in the transport and targeting of active agents.

Biological membranes form the ubiquitous delimiting structures that surround and compartmentalize all cells and organelles. The bilayer arrangement of lipids is perhaps the only organizational feature that is common to all biological membranes. Numerous theoretical models of membrane structure have appeared since the publication of the cell theory by Schleiden and Schwann in 1839. Experimental models provide insight into the motional dynamics and static structures of some isolated compartments of biological membranes. Although developed for basic research, many technological innovations have arisen from the applications of these models. Lipid vesicles have evolved successfully, as vehicles for controlled delivery.

Conventional chemotherapy for the treatment of intracellular infections is not effective, due to limited permeation of drugs into cells. This can be overcome by use of vesicular drug delivery systems. Encapsulation of a drug in vesicular structures can be predicted to prolong the existence of the drug in systemic circulation and perhaps reduce the toxicity if selective uptake can be achieved. The phagocytic uptake of the systemic delivery of the drug-loaded vesicular delivery system provides an efficient method for delivery of drug directly to the site of infection, leading to a reduction of drug toxicity with no adverse effects. Vesicular drug delivery systems

delay drug elimination of rapidly metabolizable drugs, and function as sustained release systems. This system solves the problems of drug insolubility, instability, and rapid degradation. Consequently, a number of vesicular delivery systems such as liposomes, niosomes, pharmacosomes, etc, were developed.

Niosomally Entrapped Agents³

Various bioactive agents entrapped in niosomes are Sodium stibogluconate, Methotrexate, Vincristine, Doxorubicin, Diclofenac sodium, Bovine Serum Albumin, 9-Desglycinamide 8-Arginine Vasopressin, Insulin, Estradiol, Antipyrine, Diclofenac sodium, Hemoglobin, Acyclovir, Nimesulide, Tenoxicam, Ketoprofen, Indomethacin, Pentoxifylline, Ketoconazole, Plumbagin, Primaquine, Daunorubicin, etc

Nonionic Surfactants⁴

Nonionic surfactants, as a group, find wide application in pharmaceutical and cosmetic products of all types. They are compatible with the other three classes of surfactants and retain this utility over a broad range of pH values. Their HLBs can range from about 2 upto about 18, depending on structure. Chemically, they include esters, ethers, amides and related compounds.

As a rule, chemicals in this class act as surfactants only if they carry at least one free OH group or an ether group normally derived from ethylene or propylene oxide.

Types of Niosomes³

The types of niosomes are

- 1) Multilamellar vesicles (MLV), size >0.05 μm .
- 2) Small unilamellar vesicles (SUV), size 0.025-0.05 μm .
- 3) Large unilamellar vesicles (LUV), size >0.10 μm .

Methods of Preparation of Niosomes⁵

Different types of niosomes are prepared as follows

(A) Preparation of Multilamellar Vesicles

- 1) Hand Shaking Method

(B) Preparation of Small Unilamellar Vesicles

- 1) Sonication
- 2) French Press Method
- 3) Homogenization

(C) Preparation of Large Unilamellar Vesicles

Large unilamellar vesicles are prepared by the following methods:

- 1) Reverse Phase Evaporation Method
- 2) Calcium Induced Method
- 3) Dehydration / Rehydration Of Small Unilamellar Vesicles
- 4) Detergent Removal Method
- 5) Extrusion
- 6) Ether Injection Method
- 7) Ethanol Injection Method

Entrapment Efficiency

Diclofenac sodium is encapsulated in niosomes by suitable method. After the encapsulation process is completed, unentrapped drug is separated by dialysis, centrifugation and gel chromatography. The remaining entrapped drug in niosomes is determined by lysing the vesicles using 50% n-propanol or 0.1% Triton x-100 or sodium lauryl sulphate and the entrapped efficiency (EE) of the drug is calculated by

$$EE = \frac{\text{Amount Entrapped}}{\text{Total Amount Added}} \times 100$$

using the formula:

In Vitro Drug Release Rates

Release of the drug from the vesicles can be monitored by dialyzing the diluted niosomal suspension against buffer at definite temperature and determining the drug content of dialysate.

Proniosomes⁵

Proniosomes are dry formulations of surfactant-coated carrier, which can be measured out as needed and rehydrated by brief agitation in hot water. These "proniosomes" minimize problems of niosome physical stability such as aggregation, fusion and leaking, and provide additional convenience in transportation, distribution, storage and dosing.

Proniosome-derived niosomes are superior to conventional niosomes in convenience of storage, transport and dosing. Stability of dry proniosomes is expected to be more stable than a pre-manufactured niosomal suspension. In release studies, proniosomes appear to be equivalent to conventional niosomes. Size distributions of proniosome-derived niosomes are somewhat better than those of conventional niosomes, so the release performance in more critical cases turns out to be superior.

Proniosomes are dry powder, which makes further processing and packaging possible. The powder form provides optimal flexibility, unit dosing, in which the proniosome powder is provided in capsule could be beneficial.

The aim of this present work is to formulate Diclofenac sodium proniosomes by slurry method using surfactant, span 80.

Materials

In this study we we were Procured Diclofenac sodium From Glen mark generic Ltd, Mumbai as agift Sample,and used Excipients as Cholesterol, Span 80, Diethyl ether and Sodium Lauryl Sulphate.

Methods

Construction of Standard Curve for Diclofenac sodium

Diclofenac sodium can be estimated spectrometrically at 445 nm as it obeys Beer's-Lambert's law limit is the range of 2-18 mcg/ml.

Preparation of Standard Drug Solution

Stock Solution

100mg of diclofenac sodium was dissolved in 100ml of methanol so as to get a stock solution of 1000 µg/ml concentration.

Standard Solution

2 ml of stock solution was made to 100ml with phosphate buffer saline pH 7.4 thus giving a concentration of 20 µg/ml. Aliquot of standard drug solution ranging from 1ml to 9ml were transferred in to 10ml volumetric flask and were diluted up to the mark with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. Thus the final concentration ranges from 2-18 µg/ml. Absorbance of each solution was measured at 445 nm against phosphate buffer saline pH 7.4 as a blank. A plot of concentrations of drug vs. absorbance was plotted.

Table 1 Data's For Standard Curve

S.No	Concentration (µg/ ml)	Absorbance (445nm)
1	2	0.132
2	4	0.224
3	6	0.326
4	8	0.426
5	10	0.524
6	12	0.627
7	14	0.731
8	16	0.796
9	18	0.892
Slope		0.0257
Regression value		0.9976

Figure 1 Standard Curve for Diclofenac sodium

Formulation of Proniosomes

The model drug Diclofenac sodium is to be formulated as proniosomes having different ratios of cholesterol and Surfactant (Span 80).

Evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium Proniosome Powder

The prepared Diclofenac sodium proniosome powder is to be evaluated for the following parameters

1. Angle of repose.
2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).
3. Rehydration characteristics.

Evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium Proniosome Dispersion (After Reconstitution)

The Diclofenac sodium proniosomes powder are to be reconstituted before use by distilled water. The proniosomes suspension after reconstitution is to be evaluated for the following

1. Osmotic shock.
2. Drug entrapment.
3. Vesicle size and shape.

The impact of cholesterol and surfactant in the formulation is to be studied by increasing the concentration of the above in the formulation.

The quantity of drug loaded in the formulation is increased, to assess the efficiency of the proniosomes to incorporate large doses of drug.

Scale UP

The suitability for scale up of the proniosome formulation is to be tested and compared with conventional niosomes

Preparation of Proniosomes

The slurry method is selected for the preparation of proniosomes using maltodextrin as a carrier. The drug solution is added to the surfactant mixture, which contains ether, surfactant and cholesterol. The resultant solution is added to the flask containing maltodextrin. It is rotated in the rotary shaker to get the maltodextrin coated with surfactant mixture. Meanwhile if necessary it is kept in the water bath to evaporate the ether from the flask.

Table 2 Formulations of proniosomes

Formulation code	Drug (mg)	Span 80 (mg)	Cholesterol (mg)	Diethyl ether (ml)	Maltodextrin (mg)	Rehydration Volume(ml)
PRNIO1	50	50	50	10	1000	10
PRNIO 2	50	100	50	10	1000	10
PRNIO 3	50	50	100	10	1000	10
SCNIO	250	250	250	50	5000	50

Proniosome-derived niosome dispersions were obtained by hydrating the proniosome preparation

with 80°C distilled water and vortexed for a min. the resulting niosome dispersion was used for the

determination of the entrapment efficiency, particle size analysis and morphological studies.

Drug containing proniosome- derived niosomes can be prepared by adding drug (Diclofenac sodium) to the surfactant mixture prior to the addition of surfactant mixture onto the maltodextrin or by addition of drug to the aqueous solution (distilled water) used to dissolve the maltodextrin.

Evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium Proniosome Powder

The proniosome dry powder was evaluated for its powder characteristics namely

- 1) Angle of repose.
- 2) Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).
- 3) Rehydration characteristics.

Angle of repose:

The powder was passed through the funnel until it forms a pile. Height and radius of base of pile was noted. The angle of repose can be calculated by using the formula,

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}h/r.$$

where

- θ = Angle of repose in degrees
- h = height of the pile in cm.
- r = radius of the pile in cm.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):

Small amount of powder sample was sprinkled over fevicol adhesive on the specimen stub. It was then coated with gold using Hitachi Vacuum Evaporator, Model HUS 5 GB. Coated samples were analysed in a Hitachi Scanning Electron Microscope Model S-150 and photographed. Coating was done after evaporation of liquid in case of liquid samples.

Rehydration characteristics:

The prepared Diclofenac sodium proniosome powder was rehydrated with different volumes of distilled water. Proniosomes were rehydrated with 5 ml, 10 ml, and 15 ml of distilled water and observed for vesicles.

Evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium Proniosome Dispersion (After Reconstitution)

The Diclofenac sodium proniosome powder was reconstituted with distilled water to form dispersion. The prepared dispersion was evaluated for

1. Osmotic shock.
2. Drug entrapment.
3. Vesicle size and shape.

Osmotic shock

The effect of osmotic shock was studied for all proniosome formulations and conventional niosomes. The effect of osmotic shock was investigated by observing the vesicle size by optical microscope following the incubation of the vesicular suspension in media of different tonicity (45 ml).

A hypertonic media is simulated by 1.5% NaCl, normal saline with 0.9% NaCl and hypotonic media with 0.5% NaCl. The vesicular suspension was incubated in these media for 3 hr following which the

change in vesicle size was observed under optical microscope. At each hr the samples were taken and analysed for the presence of drug. At each time when an aliquot of samples were withdrawn, the same quantity of media was replaced to the beaker.

Vesicle Size and Shape

The optical microscopy can be used for vesicles of size range of about 20μ . Vesicle of size range below 20μ cannot be determined by optical microscope since the calibration factor itself about 16μ . Vesicles below 20μ can be effectively analysed by SEM or TEM. The shape and surface characteristics of vesicles can be studied by magnifying the individual vesicle obtained from SEM or TEM photographs.

The SEM photographs were taken for reconstituted proniosome dispersions.

Scale UP

The suitability of the formulations for large-scale manufacturing was tested by increasing the quantity of the ingredients used. The prepared formulations are then examined for physical characters namely formation of vesicles and shape of vesicle by optical microscopy.

Proniosomes

The amount of ingredients was raised to 5 times. The prepared niosomes were examined for vesicle formation upon hydration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Angle of Repose

Angle of repose was measured for PRNIO 1 and maltodextrin powder. Results of measurements of angle of repose of proniosome powder and maltodextrin were summarized in table.6

Table 3 Angle of repose

Formulation Code	Angle of repose*
PRNIO 1	$38.2^0 \pm 1.12$
Maltodextrin	$37.4^0 \pm 0.58$

* Indicates average of three values.

Results indicate that the angle of repose of dry proniosome powder is nearly equal to that of pure maltodextrin.

This shows that the prepared proniosome formulations have appreciable flow properties and rehydration of formulations could be easy.

SEM [Powder Morphology]

Proniosome powder particle (before reconstitution) is magnified at 600 X. The shapes of uncoated maltodextrin were mostly spherical and smooth surface whereas dry proniosome was irregular and nearly spherical. Many adhered particles were on the surface. This shows that there was deformation after adding surfactant mixture to the carrier. Proniosome powder ranges from 250μ - 1700μ .

SEM PHOTOS

Figure 1 SEM photograph of Diclofenac sodium encapsulated proniosome (Prnio 1)

Rehydration Characteristics

5, 10, 15 ml of distilled water were added to PRNIO 1 formulation. They are rehydrated by agitation or shaking, Niosomal dispersions were obtained when different volumes were added to proniosome powder. All the dispersions give niosomal vesicles when viewed under optical microscope.

Table 4 Rehydration Characteristics

Formulation Code	Rehydration volume	Formation of vesicles
Prnio 1	5 ml	+++
Prnio 1	10 ml	+++
Prnio 1	15 ml	+++

Osmotic Shock

All the formulations were subjected to osmotic shock study by incubating in 45 ml each of three tonicity media for 3 hrs. After 3 hr, the vesicle size was observed under optical microscope. Vesicles of all the formulations that are incubated in 0.5% NaCl and 1.5 % NaCl were swelled and shrunked respectively. Whereas the size of vesicles of the formulation incubated in 0.9 % NaCl was unchanged.

Table 5 Average vesicle size for Diclofenac sodium proniosomal formulation

Formulation Code	Average vesicle size (μm) after incubation with			
	PBS (pH 7.4)	1.5 % w/v NaCl	0.9 % w/v NaCl	0.5 % w/v NaCl
PRNIO 1	4.27	Shrunked	3.43	6.34
PRNIO 2	4.88	Shrunked	4.71	6.96
PRNIO 3	4.17	Shrunked	4.22	7.09

Figure 2 Niosome vesicles (400 X) on reconstitution of proniosome powder (PRNIO1)

Drug Entrapment

Table 6 Drug entrapment

Formulation Code	% Drug entrapment
PRNIO 1	76.8
PRNIO 2	85.6
PRNIO 3	88.2

CONCLUSION:

- Diclofenac sodium loaded proniosomes can be prepared by slurry method with Span 80 and cholesterol in the ratio of 1:1, 2:1, and 1:2.
- The powder is smooth surface both visually and microscopically. The Most of the vesicles are spherical in shape, the size range of the vesicles.
- The scale up of the formulation can only be possible when it is prepared in powder (proniosome) form. When the ingredients in normal niosomal formula were raised, an incomplete lipid film was observed leading to unsuccessful formulation.
- The main objective of the present study was to perform the drug entrapment study by aqueous drug determination method. There are two methods available to carry out drug entrapment studies. They are aqueous drug determination method and lysis method. The former method is involved in the estimation of untrapped drug while the latter method

is based on the drug entrapped in the vesicles. The latter method need the sample to be dialysed to remove untrapped drug. Moreover, there may be some chance of hindrances in the spectroscopic determination of drug along with the lysing agent in the sample.

- Niosomal dispersions were obtained when different volumes (5,10 and 10 ml) were added to proniosome powder.
- High % drug entrapment was observed in the formulation PRNIO 3.

Osmotic shock studies on vesicles showed that no significant change in the niosomal preparation was stored at normal saline.

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